

DIGITAL INDUSTRIES SOFTWARE

Supporting automated driving systems development with synthetic data

Verifying and validating automated driving systems by combining real-world and synthetic data via simulations

Executive summary

This white paper explores the general benefits and drawbacks of synthetic data and highlights Simcenter™ Prescan software capabilities for generating high fidelity synthetic data. Simcenter is part of the Siemens Xcelerator business platform of software, hardware and services.

Autonomous driving systems (ADS) require vast amounts of labeled data for training and validation tasks applied in object detection, semantic segmentation, lane following and sensor fusion. Due to the cost and complexity of collecting real-world data, synthetic datasets, generated by using simulators and 3D engines, have become increasingly important.

Therefore, engineers must generate synthetic data using high-fidelity computer simulations, which can significantly accelerate the development of ADS and artificial intelligence (AI)-based systems while reducing development costs.

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Introduction

Synthetic data is information that is artificially generated rather than produced by real-world events.¹ Using computer simulations, synthetic data is generated and deployed to train and/or validate machine learning models.

Synthetic data generation encompasses most applications of physical modeling, such as music synthesizers or flight simulators. The output of such systems approximates the real thing; however, computers can fully algorithmically generate it.²

Synthetic data is generated to meet specific needs or certain conditions that may not be found in the original, real-world data and is often generated to represent authentic data and allows a baseline to be set. One of the benefits of synthetic data is to protect the privacy and confidentiality of authentic data.³

Figure 1 shows a typical data-driven workflow (continuous integration and deployment) that engineers can apply to develop an automated driving system.⁴ In this workflow, the synthetic data and/or high-fidelity simulations allow designers to further improve and refine the design.

Figure 1. A data-driven workflow for developing an automated driving system.⁴

Due to the ability to model real-life scenarios, designers can obtain feedback on how a concept will behave in the real world (for example, in the case of safety critical traffic scenarios, a large variation of vulnerable road users), even before deployment. In addition, the generated synthetic dataset allows verification and validation (V&V) at early stages of various data processing pipelines.

Overview of various publicly available synthetic datasets

Autonomous driving systems require vast amounts of labeled data for training and validation tasks applied in object detection, semantic segmentation, lane following and sensor fusion. Due to the cost and complexity of collecting real-world data, synthetic datasets, generated by using simulators and 3D engines, have become increasingly important.

Table 1 illustrates a breakdown of major synthetic datasets and how they compare to one another.^{5, 6}

Dataset	Lidar	Radar	RGB	Depth	Segmentation	Ground truth	Variations
SYNTHIA ⁷	—	—	✓	✓	✓	Limited 3D boxes	Weather, seasons, angles
Virtual KITTI ⁸	—	—	✓	✓	✓	Tracking, flow, boxes	Lighting, camera view
GTA V-Based (VIPER) ⁹	✓	—	✓	✓	✓	Boxes, flow, tracking	Day/night, weather, occlusion
DeepDrive UDD ¹⁰	—	—	✓	—	✓	2D boxes	Weather, view
RealDriveSim ⁶	—	—	✓	✓	✓	2D and 3D scene flow	Weather

Table 1. Publicly available synthetic data sets.

Benefits and drawbacks of using synthetic data in V&V for ADS

In this section we briefly compare synthetic data and real-world data used in verifying and validating automated driving systems (see figure 2).

Real-world data or V&V in a physical environment has the main advantage of realism; however, there are several drawbacks. For example, there are excessive costs due to vehicle instrumentation, data collection campaigns and data storage. Additionally, data privacy issues, data annotation, data labeling and extracting reliable ground truth data can be costly. Another drawback is that data might be unavailable early in development or might be incomplete.

To overcome these drawbacks, synthetic data might be useful since it:

- Comes with lower costs
- Could be available at an early development process stage

- Can achieve higher completeness compared to real-world data (it can include corner cases and edge cases, which are difficult to capture in the real world)
- Does not need expensive annotation and labeling for the ground truth data
- Has no privacy issues

Despite these advantages, synthetic data is imperfect and should be used wisely in combination with real-world data since it has a lower level of realism. Generating synthetic data using simulation requires qualified simulation environments and skilled engineers with expertise in computer science, environment and sensor modeling and model validation.

	Pros	Cons
Real-world data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High level of realism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High costs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Vehicle instrumentation: sensors, DAQ – Data collection and data storage – Privacy, annotation, labeling, ground truth • Non-availability (in time) of the data • Data might not be complete
Synthetic data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower costs • Availability (in less time) of the data • Completeness of the data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Different illumination and weather conditions – Corner cases, edge cases – Ground truth availability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower level of realism • Expertise in modeling and simulations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Environment modeling – Sensor set-up modeling – Sensor data generation • Qualified simulation environment

Figure 2. Comparison between real-world and synthetic data.

Synthetic data generation for automated driving systems

The first step in establishing an automated driving system’s capability is defining its operational design domain (ODD), where the taxonomy is in accordance with the British Standards Institution (BSI) publicly available specification (PAS) 1883, as seen in figure 3.

Figure 3. ODD taxonomy according to BSI PAS 1883.

The next steps are defining the dynamic driving task and requirements elicitation according to applicable legislation and standards.

To illustrate synthetic data generation and to explore possible applications, we modeled a typical urban driving scenario in Simcenter Prescan, where the vehicle is approaching a pedestrian crosswalk and a pedestrian is crossing the road.¹¹

It is required to simulate the same scenario with different illuminations, weather conditions and dynamic actors, for example, various vulnerable road users.

Table 2 summarizes the variations we applied in the simulation and figure 4 shows the camera visualizations (some samples) we used Simcenter Prescan to simulate.

Seasons	Summer, spring-autumn and winter
Weather type	Clear, rain, light snow, snow, light fog and dense fog
Time of day	05:00, 06:00, 08:00, 09:00, 12:00, 15:00, 17:00, 19:00 and 21:00
Cloud coverage and sun settings	Derived from season, weather type and time of day
Vulnerable road user	Regular male, female with child in a stroller, female with a shopping cart, child and male with a bicycle

Table 2. Variations applied in simulation during synthetic data generation.

Figure 4. Synthetic camera images we generated using Simcenter Prescan.¹¹

The Simcenter Prescan simulation environment has various predefined sensor models, with the possibility to adjust or tune certain parameters. This enables us to generate synthetic data related to various virtual sensors such as a physics-based camera, radar, lidar and ideal depth map, which figure 5 shows.

Physics-based camera sensor

Ideal depth map

Physics-based point cloud lidar

Physics-based radar sensor

Figure 5. Synthetic data, the output of various virtual sensors, in Simcenter Prescan.¹¹

The ground truth data format extends the well-known KITTI data format with a unique object identifier (object ID) as well as object type according to Simcenter Prescan definitions, as shown in table 3.^{12, 13}

Values	Name	Description
1	object ID	Unique object ID from Simcenter Prescan.
1	object type	Object type, according to object type definition in Simcenter Prescan.
1	type	Object type, according to KITTI data format: 'Car', 'Van', 'Truck', 'Pedestrian', 'Person_sitting', 'Cyclist', 'Tram', 'Misc' or 'DontCare'.
1	truncated	Float from 0 (non-truncated) to 1 (truncated), where truncated refers to the object leaving image boundaries.
1	occluded	Integer (0,1,2,3) indicating occlusion state: 0 = fully visible, 1 = partly occluded, 2 = largely occluded, 3 = unknown.
1	alpha	Observation angle of object, ranging [-pi, pi].
4	bbox	2D bounding box of object in the image (0-based index): contains left, top, right, bottom pixel coordinates.
3	dimensions	3D object dimensions: height, width, length (in meters).
3	Location	3D object location x, y, z in camera coordinates (in meters).
1	Rotation_y	Rotation around Y-axis in camera coordinates [-pi, pi].
1	Score	Only for results: Flot, indicating confidence in detection, needed for p/r curves, higher is better.

Table 3. Simcenter Prescan synthetic data ground truth data structure.

Sensor modeling in Simcenter Prescan

Generating synthetic data with high realism requires environment modeling with high fidelity and proper sensor models.

Leveraging Simcenter Prescan offers validated physics-based sensors that model the effect of various environmental conditions. Hence, we can ensure the generated synthetic data will consider the environmental conditions and the effect of various material properties. The sensor suite we selected for generating this synthetic data is as follows.

We used the Simcenter Prescan physics-based radar scene simulator (RSS) to produce a 4D imaging radar output of the scene. This device-agnostic sensor produces point cloud like outputs, which state-of-the-art radar perception algorithms can consume or use as training for developing radar perception models.

Figure 6 shows a visualization of a sample output of this sensor. We modeled this sensor using an operating frequency of 77 gigahertz (GHz) with a transmitter power of 20 decibel-milliwatts (dBm) and a 120-degree field of view looking in front of the car with a maximum detection range of 120 meters (m). To ensure we captured and generated sufficient

points, we chose a power threshold of -150 decibels (dB) to filter the points.

Using the Simcenter Prescan physics-based camera, we generated synthetic red, green, blue (RGB) images of the simulated scenario from the perspective of a camera mounted on the front of the car. Figure 6 shows a sample RGB image simulated in Simcenter Prescan during one of the sample scenarios. We modeled the camera as a generic RGB high definition (HD), for example, 1280x960 resolution, automotive camera operating at 20 frames per second (FPS).

We then used the Simcenter Prescan physics-based lidar to generate the synthetic lidar model. For this, we used an Ouster OS0 64 layers uniform lidar,¹⁴ which we modeled in Simcenter Prescan to mimic the scan and firing pattern of the physical device in simulation. Figure 6 shows a sample output of the simulated Ouster OS0 64 in Simcenter Prescan.

This ground truth data provides information about the objects around the vehicle such as distance to targets, target orientation, object types, occlusion and truncation rates. In addition, this data can be used during training and/or validating AI-based systems.

Figure 6. Synthetic data generation examples showing the radar point cloud (left), camera (middle) and lidar point cloud (right).

Sensor model validation and simulation credibility

For a trustworthy simulation, we need to validate the sensors and environment model. Using Simcenter Prescan, we can model three key pillars to ensure a validated physics-based sensor simulation, as shown in figure 7.

Figure 7. The three pillars for trustworthy sensor simulation.

By partnering with original equipment manufacturers (OEMs), Siemens conducted studies to validate the three simulation components. In the following paragraphs, we will focus on the validation studies we performed using Simcenter Prescan leveraging lidar, radar and camera sensors.

To validate the Simcenter Prescan lidar sensor, we proposed and executed a comprehensive three-step approach together with XenomatiX.¹⁵

The first step involved specific tests under controlled laboratory conditions, where we used XenomatiX's

XenoLidar to test four targets, including car paint and retroreflective signs.

The second step transitions to a semi-controlled environment (parking lot) where we took measurements with vehicle-mounted sensors and compared them against a digital twin we created in Simcenter Prescan. This validation process includes detailed measurements of material properties, including bidirectional scattering and distribution functions (BSDFs) at 840 nanometer (nm) infrared wavelength, ensuring accurate simulation of energy reflections.

The final validation step involved testing under normal driving conditions, where we collected and compared real-world data qualitatively with simulated scenarios, which provided strong confidence.

Using Simcenter Prescan, we performed a validation study of a physics-based radar sensor, where we verified several critical aspects of the simulation, including the radar cross-section (RCS) measurements. These measurements showed a decent similarity between simulated and measured results for simple objects and complex vehicles.

The simulation accurately modeled physical properties of the radar sensor, including transmit power, waveform, antenna patterns, receiver gain and noise properties. It also incorporated sophisticated features such as clutter simulation, micro-Doppler effects and realistic thermal and phase noise.¹⁶

With the obtained results, we confirmed the capability of using Simcenter Prescan to accurately represent complex real-world scenarios and radar-specific phenomena. This includes successfully simulating micro-Doppler signatures from vehicle wheels and Doppler velocity measurements of multiple vehicles as well as reproducing ghost targets caused by multiple bounces in realistic traffic situations.

The simulation proved valuable in complex scenarios, such as when vehicles pass buildings or other cars, demonstrating its capability to handle occluded targets and multiple reflections that match real-world radar behavior.

Finally, we also followed a similar methodology for internally validating Simcenter Prescan physics-based camera simulations by combining controlled laboratory testing and semi-controlled environmental validation. The study focused on fundamental camera characteristics under controlled conditions, where we tested specific aspects, such as shading, lens distortion, color reproduction and photometric accuracy, against real-world camera measurements. We computed a rating score for each specific aspect of the camera with an average total rating of over 90 percent.

Further, several automotive customers using Simcenter Prescan have independently validated specific aspects of the camera simulation in semi-controlled outdoor environments, confirming accurate reproduction of lens distortion effects, high dynamic range (HDR) behavior and color fidelity across various environmental conditions.

Conclusion

Synthetic data contributes to accelerating and reducing the cost of AI-based systems and automated driving systems development. Despite these advantages, synthetic data is imperfect and should be used wisely in combination with real-world data since synthetic data has a lower level of realism.

In addition, generating synthetic data using simulation requires qualified simulation environments and skilled engineers with expertise in computer science, environment and sensor modeling and model validation.

Leveraging the Simcenter Prescan simulation environment offers validated physics-based sensors that model the effect of various environmental conditions. Therefore, users can ensure the generated synthetic data will consider the environmental conditions and the effect of various material properties. The sensor suite includes a physics-based camera, radar, lidar sensors and ground truth sensors, making it a valuable tool for automated driving systems developers.

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